

Chemical reaction pathways of the Al + (H₂O)_n systems (n=1–4)

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Received: February 15, 2017, Accepted: March 18, 2017, Published: March 18, 2017.

ABSTRACT

The systematic study of the growth of water clusters is of interest. The potential energy profiles for the reactions Al+(H₂O)_n, (n=1–4) have been investigated in detail using DFT as well as the *ab initio* method. Final energies have been evaluated at the CCSD(T)/6–311G(d,p)//B3LYP/6–311G(d,p)+ZPE level. All the stationary points have been located. Structurally, the stationary points on the Al+(H₂O)_n potential energy surfaces are related. Energetically, the water tetramer reaction Al+(H₂O)₄, water trimer reaction Al+(H₂O)₃, and water dimer reaction Al+(H₂O)₂ are barrierless, while the water monomer reaction Al+H₂O has a ~8 kcal/mol barrier. The reaction yielding AlH and (H₂O)_{n-1}OH was calculated to be highly endothermic.

Keywords: Aluminum, cluster, CCSD(T), DFT, IRC, water.

INTRODUCTION

The key species of this theoretical work are water and aluminum. Both species and their derived compounds were each about theoretical and experimental researches [1-13]. Reactions involving water are important to atmospheric, environmental, and combustion chemistry. The reaction of aluminum with water in the gas phase is currently under intense investigation. For example, aluminum and water as propellants have been proposed for application in both space [14-16] and underwater propulsion [17, 18]. For propulsion systems, if the reaction takes place between metal fuels and water, the specific impulse will be remarkably increased. The reaction of metal and H₂O applied as the energy of propulsion has a notable volume energy density because it does not bear the weight of water under the water propulsion system. However, because of the higher melting and boiling point of Al and its oxide coating, the reaction activity of Al-H₂O is lower. Moreover, the start-up of reaction Al-H₂O is more difficult. These facts indicate that it is enormously difficult to make the Al-H₂O propulsion system usable in practice unless nano-sized Al particles are used. As for the energetic density, the amounts of producing gas, the stability of storing, price, and so on, the reaction of Al with H₂O is the best in metal-fuels system. Furthermore, the reaction of Al-H₂O with high energetic density can attain better propulsion performance.

We can also remember that aluminum is widely used as an ingredient for solid and liquid propellants and in explosives to increase the reaction heat release. In the past, great interest was expressed in the combustion of aluminum nanoparticles. As was shown, the usage of nanoparticles makes it possible to decrease the ignition temperature and to noticeably shorten the ignition delay as compared to burning the submicrometer particles [19–22]. One of the most important species to react with aluminum in the gas phase is steam [23, 24].

The aluminum atom plus gas-phase water reaction Al + H₂O has been extensively studied both experimentally [25–27] and theoretically [28–30]. Research on small water polymer reactions establishes important steps from discrete gas-phase water species

(monomer, dimer, trimer, etc.) to water vapor to liquid water [31, 32].

However, there are few studies on the reaction mechanism of Al with H₂O clusters. To reveal the detailed reaction mechanism and to enrich data concerning the vapor phase reaction of Al-(H₂O)_n (n=1–4) system, here we study the reactions mechanisms of Al with (H₂O)_n by a theoretical method.

2 Computational methods

All calculations were carried out using Gaussian 09 [33]. The geometry of all reactants, entrance complexes, exit complexes, transition states and products have been optimized using the DFT method at the B3LYP/6–311G (d,p) of theory, followed by harmonic vibrational frequency calculations. Intermediates complexes possess all real frequencies, whereas the transition states (TS) possess only one imaginary frequency. The zero-point energy (ZPE) corrections were carried out at the B3LYP/6–311G (d,p) level. The ZPEs were scaled up by the factor 0.9153 [34]. To explicitly establish the relevant species, the intrinsic reaction coordinate (IRC) [35, 36] was also calculated for all the transition states that appear on the energy surface profile to confirm also that the transition states connect the designated entrance complexes (EnC) and exit ones (ExC). In order to improve accuracy of the energetic results, single point calculations were performed based on the B3LYP/6–311G (d,p) optimized geometries at the CCSD(T)/6–311G(d,p) level. This level of calculations has been successfully used to study similar processes [37–39]. Final energies were calculated at the CCSD (T)/6–311G (d,p)//B3LYP/6–311G(d,p)+ZPE level.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Reaction I: Al + water monomer

The optimized geometries of the reactants, entrance complex, exit complex, transition state and products involved in the reaction of Al with H₂O are shown in Fig.1. With the Al atom approaching one H₂O molecule, a Al•••OH₂ entrance complex formed. The most important feature of the potential energy surface of the

reaction $\text{Al}+\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is this entrance complex EnC1 . In EnC1 , the forming $\text{Al}-\text{O}$ bond length is 2.220 \AA and other two $\text{O}-\text{H}$ bond lengths are 0.964 \AA which is only 0.002 \AA longer than those in the H_2O molecule. The energy of EnC1 relative to that of the separated reactants $\text{Al}+\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is 7.9 kcal/mol at the $\text{CCSD (T)/6-311G (d,p)//B3LYP/6-311G(d,p)+ZPE}$ level. Some earlier studies [25] have found very similar results with a maximum relative error of 4% for lengths while it is 0.1 % for angles. There is also an exit complex $\text{HAl}-\text{OH}$, which is 41.2 kcal/mol below the separated reactants $\text{Al}+\text{H}_2\text{O}$, at the $\text{CCSD (T)/6-311G (d,p)//B3LYP/6-311G(d,p)+ZPE}$ level. As shown in Fig. 2, compared with the separated products $\text{HAl}+\text{OH}$, the $\text{HAl}-\text{OH}$ complex is bound by 83.3 kcal/mol . The $\text{Al}+\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{HAl}+\text{OH}$ reaction is predicted to be endothermic by 42.1 kcal/mol .

It is indisputable that the IRC calculation shows that transition state TS1 connects EnC1 and the trans-isomer of complex ExC1 at $\text{B3LYP/6-311G(d,p)+ZPE}$ level. The cis isomer of exit complex (cis- ExC1) can also be considered, however, it is less stable than the trans one (trans- ExC1). The $\text{CCSD (T)/6-311G (d,p)//B3LYP/6-311G(d,p)+ZPE}$ trans-exit well lies $\sim 1 \text{ kcal/mol}$ below the cis one.

Fig 1. Optimized geometries of the species involved during the reaction (I) between Al and H_2O monomer. Bond lengths are in Å and bond angles in degrees

Fig 2. Potential energy surface, reaction energies (kcal/ mol) and activation barrier energies (kcal/ mol) for reaction (I) between Al and H_2O

Reaction II: $\text{Al} + \text{water dimer}$

The potential energy profile for the reaction $\text{Al}+(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2 \rightarrow \text{HAl}+(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{OH}$ was studied using the DFT method with a

plausible set of bases $6-311\text{G (d, p)}$. As seen in Fig. 3, reaction II begins with the formation of the entrance complex $\text{EnC2} \equiv \text{Al} \cdots (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ part of which is very similar to the complex $\text{EnC1} \equiv \text{Al} \cdots \text{H}_2\text{O}$, but attached to a second molecule of water H_2O . Our calculations at the $\text{CCSD (T)/6-311G (d, p)//B3LYP/6-311G (d, p)+ZPE}$ level show that EnC2 is 13.6 kcal/mol energetically below the separate reactants $\text{Al}+(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$. This confirms that the aluminum atom Al and water dimer $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ in the complex EnC2 is in a significantly bound state of 5.7 kcal/mol that in the case of complex EnC1 . Below the reactants an energy barrier of 1.6 kcal/mol succeeds the second entrance complex EnC2 in this study. Thus, the reaction of an aluminum atom and water dimer $\text{Al}+(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ is qualitatively different (4.7 kcal/mol) of its reaction with the monomer water $\text{Al}+\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The second water molecule intervenes here as a simple catalyst, eliminating the energy barrier for the reaction of water with monomer aluminum $\text{Al}+\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

The water dimer reaction exit complex $\text{ExC2} \equiv \text{HAl} \cdots (\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{OH}$ lies 52.6 kcal/mol below separated reactants $\text{Al}+(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$. This $\text{HAl} \cdots (\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{OH}$ exit complex lies 94.3 kcal/mol below the separated products $\text{HAl}+(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{OH}$, at the $\text{CCSD (T)/6-311G (d,p)//B3LYP/6-311G(d, p)+ZPE}$ level, compared to 83.3 kcal/mol for the analogous water monomer system. The $\text{Al}+(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2 \rightarrow \text{HAl}+(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{OH}$ reaction is predicted to be endothermic by 41.7 kcal/mol .

Fig 3. Optimized geometries of the species involved during the reaction (II) between Al and $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ dimer. Bond lengths are in Å and bond angles in degrees

Fig 4. Potential energy surface, reaction energies (kcal/ mol) and activation barrier energies (kcal/ mol) for reaction (II) between Al and $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$

Reaction III: Al + water trimer

In the case of the water trimer, we are faced with two possible important conformers baptized $uud-(H_2O)_3$ and $uuu-(H_2O)_3$ as previously studied by many researchers [40-44].

Fig 5. Optimized geometries of the two important conformers of $(H_2O)_3$ trimer. Bond lengths are in Å

Both $uud-(H_2O)_3$ and $uuu-(H_2O)_3$ are six-membered ring structures (see Fig. 5) with each water molecule functioning as both electron donor and acceptor. The ring is formed from three OH bonds connected by three hydrogen bonds. The three out-of-ring OH bonds are in either “up-up-down” (uud) or “up-up-up” (uuu) orientations, with respect to the pseudo planar six-membered ring. The uud -trimer structure is the global minimum, but the uuu -trimer structure lies higher by only 1.1 kcal/mol at the CCSD (T)/6-311G (d, p)//B3LYP/6-311G(d, p)+ZPE level of theory. During the reaction III, the attack of an aluminum atom in a trimer molecule $(H_2O)_3$ leads to entrance complex $EnC3 \equiv Al \bullet \bullet (H_2O)_3$ that is connected to the exit complex $ExC3$ through the transition state $TS3$. The entrance complex has its aluminum atom bound to one H_2O molecule, with other two H_2O molecules attached. From the entrance complex to the corresponding transition state and then to the corresponding exit complex, the distances between the aluminum atom and the hydrogen atom being abstracted decrease, forming six-membered ring structure ($ExC3$). The product $(H_2O)_2OH$ also has two conformers, $ud-(H_2O)_2OH$ and $uu-(H_2O)_2OH$, differing from each other only by the orientations of the two out-of-ring OH moieties.

Fig 6. Optimized geometries of the species involved during the reaction between Al and $(H_2O)_3$ trimer. Bond lengths are in Å

In the $EnC3$ entrance complex, the aluminum atom is bonded to the trimer $(H_2O)_3$ of two different ways: a bond to an oxygen atom (oxygen 2) and to a hydrogen atom (hydrogen 4). Thereafter, $EnC3$ undergoes, through $TS3$, a kind of exit complex rearrangement where aluminum atom Al bearing the hydrogen atom (numbered 4) is equivalently bonded to two nearest atoms

of oxygen.

As shown in Fig. 7, based on the energy pathway for the $Al+(H_2O)_3$ reaction, our CCSD (T)/6-311G (d, p)//B3LYP/6-311G(d, p)+ZPE level predicts that the $EnC3 \equiv Al \bullet \bullet (H_2O)_3$ entrance complex lying 15.4 kcal/mol below the separated reactants $Al+(H_2O)_3$ or more precisely $Al+uud-(H_2O)_3$. Compared with the entrance complex, the reaction potential barrier height predicted at the same level is 10.2 kcal/mol, but this barrier is still 5.2 kcal/mol below the reactants $Al+(H_2O)_3$. The corresponding $HAl \bullet \bullet (H_2O)_2OH$ exit complex lies ~ 444 kcal/mol below the separated products $HAl+(H_2O)_2OH$ and 59.0 kcal/mol below the separated reactants $Al+(H_2O)_3$. The $Al+uud-(H_2O)_3 \rightarrow Al+(H_2O)_2OH$ reaction is endothermic by 424.6 kcal/mol. The entrance complex wells are thus 7.9 (monomer), 13.6 (dimer), and 15.4 (trimer) kcal/mol. The energies of the transition state relative to reactants are 8.1 (monomer), -1.6 (dimer), and -5.2 (trimer) kcal/mol. Thus we see a reasonably consistent pattern of energetics.

Fig 7. Potential energy surface, reaction energies (kcal/mol) and activation barrier energies (kcal/mol) for reaction between Al and $(H_2O)_3$

Reaction IV: Al + water tetramer

The isolated water tetramer $(H_2O)_4$ system has been carefully investigated by others [45-51], and the global minimum is an eight-membered ring structure (with the rare S_4 symmetry) with each water molecule functioning as both electron donor and acceptor (see Fig. 4). The eight-membered ring is formed with four OH bonds connected by four hydrogen bonds. The four out-of-ring OH bonds are in the “up-down-up-down” ($udud$) orientation, with respect to the pseudoplanar eight-membered ring. We designate this water tetramer isomer $udud-(H_2O)_4$. Changing the orientations of the out-of-ring OH bonds from $udud-(H_2O)_4$ gives two conformers: $uudd-(H_2O)_4$ and $uddd-(H_2O)_4$, which are higher in energy than $udud-(H_2O)_4$ by only ~1 kcal/mol. There are also other isomers for the water tetramer $(H_2O)_4$ in the shape of pyramid or lasso [49,50], but both pyramid and lasso isomers have higher energies (>4 kcal/mol). Anticipating our results for $Al+(H_2O)_4$, it is fair to say that the cyclic water tetramer is rather different from the trimer. In this work, we will limit ourselves only to the reaction of Al with the most stable isomer $udud-(H_2O)_4$.

Analogous to our previous research on the $Al+(H_2O)_3$ reaction,

the stationary points on the Al+udud-(H₂O)₄ potential energy profile have been located using up to the B3LYP/6-311G(d, p) level of theory, as shown in Fig. 9, with the final energies obtained with the CCSD (T)/6-311G (d, p)//B3LYP/6-311G(d, p)+ZPE level. The Al+udud-(H₂O)₄ reaction begins with the barrierless formation of an entrance complex EnC4≡Al•••(H₂O)₄. All the four H₂O units of the isolated udud-(H₂O)₄ are equivalent. Thus, when an Al atom approaches an udud-(H₂O)₄ molecule, only one type of the Al•••(H₂O)₄ entrance complex is readily formed. We designate this Al•••(H₂O)₄ complex udud-Al•••(H₂O)₄. As shown in Fig. 8, this udud-Al•••(H₂O)₄ entrance complex has the aluminum atom bound to one water with a water trimer attached by hydrogen bonds. With the CCSD (T)/6-311G (d, p)//B3LYP/6-311G(d, p)+ZPE method, the udud-Al•••(H₂O)₄ complex is bound by 40.7 kcal/mol with respect to the separated reactants Al+udud-(H₂O)₄.

Fig 8. Optimized geometries of the species involved during the reaction between Al and (H₂O)₄ tetramer. Bond lengths are in Å

Fig 9. Potential energy surface, reaction energies (kcal/mol) and activation barrier energies (kcal/mol) for reaction between Al and (H₂O)₄

Following the udud-Al•••(H₂O)₄≡EnC4 entrance complex, we find a udud-(Al•••H)OH(H₂O)₃≡TS4 transition state. At this TS4 transition state, the distance between the aluminum atom and the hydrogen atom being abstracted, in other way, the Al-H9 distance in Fig. 8, is ~1.845Å, much shorter than the 2.650 Å found for the EnC4 entrance complex. In this way, a double cyclic structure is formed: an eight-membered ring and another three-membered, as shown in Fig. 8. The TS4 transition state structure was verified to be a first-order saddle point on the Al(H₂O)₄ potential energy surface, as it has one imaginary vibrational frequency [$\sim 1375i$ cm⁻¹ at the B3LYP/6-311G(d, p) level of theory]. The normal mode of the imaginary vibrational frequency shows simultaneous Al-H9 bond formation and O7-H9 bond rupture as the reaction proceeds toward HAl+(H₂O)₃OH. Energetically, this TS4 transition state lies 20.8 kcal/mol below the separated reactants Al+udud-(H₂O)₄ at the CCSD (T)/6-311G (d, p)//B3LYP/6-311G(d, p)+ZPE level of theory. With respect to the udud-Al•••(H₂O)₄ entrance complex the Al+udud-(H₂O)₄ reaction barrier is predicted to be 19.9 kcal/mol by the CCSD (T)/6-311G (d, p)//B3LYP/6-311G(d, p)+ZPE method.

The Al+udud-(H₂O)₄ reaction proceeds to its exit complex HAl•••(H₂O)₃OH≡ExC4, as the HAl bond is formed. The ExC4 exit complex has a pseudo-planar eight membered ring structure with its three out-of-ring OH moieties in the “down-up-down” (dud≡H12H3H5) orientation and its O7 atom is bonded to substituent HAl. The chemically bound HAl distance in this udud-HAl•••(H₂O)₃OH exit complex is 1.608 Å, somewhat shorter than the 1.667 Å for the free AlH molecule. The ExC4 exit complex is energetically 70.5 kcal/mol lower than the separated reactants Al+udud-(H₂O)₄ at the same level of theory.

The release of the HAl molecule from the udud-HAl(H₂O)₃OH exit complex gives the reaction products HAl and (H₂O)₃OH. Analogous to the reactant (H₂O)₄, the product (H₂O)₃OH has an eight-membered ring structure with four OH bonds connected by four hydrogen bonds and three out-of-ring OH bonds in an “down-up-down” (dud) orientation, with respect to the pseudoplanar eight-membered ring. Compared with the separated HAl+udu-(H₂O)₃OH products, the udu-HF•••(H₂O)₃OH exit complex is bound by 467.9 kcal/mol at the CCSD (T)/6-311G (d, p)//B3LYP/6-311G(d, p)+ZPE level of theory. The HAl+udu-(H₂O)₃OH products are predicted to lie 397.4 kcal/mol above the separated Al+udud-(H₂O)₄ reactants. Therefore, the reaction Al+(H₂O)₄ → HAl+(H₂O)₃OH is significantly endothermic, consistent with the low dissociation energy of diatomic HAl.

Comparison

It is instructive to compare the water tetramer reaction Al+(H₂O)₄ with the water trimer reaction Al+(H₂O)₃, water dimer reaction Al+(H₂O)₂, and water monomer reaction Al+H₂O. To be consistent, all the energies from the CCSD (T)/6-311G (d, p)//B3LYP/6-311G(d, p)+ZPE level are used in the following discussions, as shown in Fig. 10. Structurally, the entrance complexes for the water monomer reaction Al+H₂O, water dimer reaction Al+(H₂O)₂, water trimer reaction Al+(H₂O)₃, and water tetramer reaction Al+(H₂O)₄ are clearly related. All of the entrance complexes involve a most prominent Al•••H₂O fragment. The water tetramer entrance complex Al•••(H₂O)₄ looks like the water trimer entrance complex Al•••(H₂O)₃ to which has been inserted a fourth water molecule; or the water

dimer entrance complex $\text{Al}\cdots(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ with an $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ inserted; or the water monomer entrance complex $\text{Al}\cdots\text{OH}_2$ interacting with a $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3$ water trimer. Energetically, the water monomer complex $\text{Al}\cdots\text{OH}_2$ is predicted to be bound by 7.9 kcal/mol. The water dimer complex $\text{Al}\cdots(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ is bound by 13.6 kcal/mol, because of an additional $\text{Al}\cdots\text{HO}$ bond between the aluminum atom and the second H_2O molecule. The aluminum atom in the water trimer complex $\text{Al}\cdots(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3$ has similar binding mode noting increased donor-acceptor interaction between Al and O (short binding length in the trimer as in the dimer), and between Al and H and therefore the binding energy passes from 13.6 kcal/mol ($\text{Al}\cdots(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ complex) to 15.4 kcal/mol ($\text{Al}\cdots(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3$ complex).

The water tetramer complex $\text{Al}\cdots(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4$ also has a similar aluminum atom bridging mode to the water dimer complex $\text{Al}\cdots(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ and the water trimer complex $\text{Al}\cdots(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3$. The biggest binding energy of 40.7 kcal/mol may arise from growth of the hydrogen bonds in the tetramer complex on the one hand, and on the other hand more water molecules are added, the complex stabilizes increasingly driven H_2O concomitant donor to the acceptor effect of Al.

The transition states of these four reactions, the water tetramer transition state $\text{Al}\cdots\text{H}\cdots\text{OH}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3$, the trimer transition state $\text{Al}\cdots\text{H}\cdots\text{OH}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$, and the dimer transition state $\text{Al}\cdots\text{H}\cdots\text{OH}(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ are predicted to lie below corresponding separated reactants by 1.6, 5.2, and 20.8 kcal/mol, respectively, while the monomer transition state $\text{Al}\cdots\text{OH}_2$ lies above separated reactants Al + H_2O by 8.1 kcal/mol (Fig. 10).

Thus, the second water molecule removes the barrier, like a catalyst, from the monomer $\text{Al} + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{HAl} + \text{OH}$ reaction, lowering the barrier to -1.6 kcal/mol, due to an additional hydrogen bond similar to the situation for the entrance complex. The third water molecule further decreases the barrier to -5.2 kcal/mol.

The important point to emphasize is that the $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3$ to $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4$ passage helps to decrease significantly the barrier for the aluminum atom reaction to -20.8 kcal/mol.

Fig 10. Comparison of the potential energy profiles for the $\text{Al} + (\text{H}_2\text{O})_n$, $n = 1-4$ reactions. All the energies are obtained at the

CCSD (T)/6-311G (d, p)//B3LYP/6-311G(d, p)+ZPE level of theory.

CONCLUSION

The CCSD (T)/6-311G (d, p)//B3LYP/6-311G(d, p)+ZPE level of theory has been used to predict the potential energy profile of the aluminum atom plus the water tetramer $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4$ reaction. Due to the abundance of possible water tetramer isomer structures, the lowest-lying $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4$ structure, i.e. $\text{udud}-(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4$, is mainly considered. Based on the CCSD (T)/6-311G (d, p)//B3LYP/6-311G(d, p)+ZPE results, the $\text{Al} + \text{udud}-(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4 \rightarrow \text{HAl} + (\text{H}_2\text{O})_3\text{OH}$ reaction is endothermic by 397.4 kcal/mol. The transition state TS4 lies at 20.8 kcal/mol below the reactants, suggesting that the reaction is barrierless. There are an entrance complex EnC4 (40.5 kcal/mol lower in energy than the reactants) and an exit complex ExC4 (467.9 kcal/mol below the products). Energetically, the water tetramer reaction $\text{Al} + (\text{H}_2\text{O})_4 \rightarrow \text{HAl} + (\text{H}_2\text{O})_3\text{OH}$ is related to the water trimer reaction $\text{Al} + (\text{H}_2\text{O})_3 \rightarrow \text{HAl} + (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{OH}$ and the water dimer reaction $\text{Al} + (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2 \rightarrow \text{HAl} + (\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{OH}$, but qualitatively different from the water monomer reaction $\text{Al} + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{HAl} + \text{OH}$. This is because, structurally, the stationary points on the $\text{Al} + (\text{H}_2\text{O})_4$ potential energy surface are closely related to those on the water trimer reaction $\text{Al} + (\text{H}_2\text{O})_3$ and to the water dimer reaction $\text{Al} + (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ surfaces, but different from the water monomer reaction $\text{Al} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ surfaces. There is no barrier for the water tetramer reaction $\text{Al} + (\text{H}_2\text{O})_4$, the water trimer reaction $\text{Al} + (\text{H}_2\text{O})_3$, or the water dimer reaction $\text{Al} + (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$, while the water monomer reaction $\text{Al} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ has a barrier of about 8 kcal/mol.

Acknowledgements

This study was supported by the CNRST Kingdom of Morocco, for a project PORTAS III (N° D12/34). I would like to thank Professors M. Dagueuet and A. Belghit for their help.

Author contributions

The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

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Citation: Mustapha Cherkaoui. *et al.* (2017). Chemical reaction pathways of the $\text{Al} + (\text{H}_2\text{O})_n$ systems ($n=1-4$). , *J. of Physical and Chemical Sciences*.V5I1. DOI: 10.15297/JPCS.V5I1.03

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